

Lorentz Invariant Information and $-Et+px$ Leading to Quantum Free Particle $\hbar/p, \hbar/E$

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A free particle may be described by $x-x_0=v(t-t_0)$ and $E=mc^2/\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$, $p = m_0 v/\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$ (one dimension). It seems, in fact, that this is the usual way in which one considers the particle even if one uses special relativity.

We have pointed out in previous notes that if one considers the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$, then there exists a degeneracy, $x_0 + n \cdot \hbar/p$ and $t_0 + n \cdot \hbar/E$ ((1)), where n is an integer. This degeneracy only appears, however, if one uses $-Et+px$, and one might argue that there is no reason to do so. The description in the first paragraph does not introduce any degeneracy.

We argue that a particle at rest with m_0 at $x=0$, t may be viewed from many different frames moving with different constant speeds $-v(i)$, where i denotes the particular speed. One may use the prescription in the first paragraph for each, but physically these are all different views of the same m_0 at $x=0$, $t=0$ state and we suggest that the Lorentz invariant information $-Et+px$ conveys this important idea. As a result, $A=-Et+px$ is an important piece of information relevant to the system if one wishes to study it in a Lorentz invariant manner. If that is the case, then the degeneracy ((1)) is very important because it essentially removes information from A , i.e. $A=0$ for the x and t resolutions, but places them in space. Given that A for x_0, t_0 cannot be distinguished from the other points, this suggests that one has fixed resolution in space because the Lorentz invariant information is the same at each degenerate point. One may note that transforming the resolutions using a Lorentz transformation leads to degenerate points in the prime frame as expected.

Momentum and energy are state properties which must hold at all x, t and $x=vt$ still holds and gives the sense of uniform space. As a result, one must find a picture that combines the view of the first paragraph with the Lorentz invariant information view and that leads to $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$.

The Reason for $-Et+px$

If one has a particle with rest mass, m_0 , at rest at $x=0$, t , then in a moving frame with constant $-v$, it is seen to move with v . As a result, one might consider creating a 2×2 matrix to transform $(x=0, t)$ to the moving frame (x', t') such that $x'/t'=v$. This, however, does not lead immediately to any notion of E or p , but nonrelativistically one knows that a moving particle should have both. The question then becomes: Does the same transformation hold for $(x=0, t)$ and $(p=0, m_0)$? A clue that it might follow from the nonrelativistic free particle equations:

$$p=mv \text{ and } x=vt \quad ((2))$$

Here x follows by multiplying t by v and p by multiplying m_0 (which may be thought of as rest energy). ((2)) shows that both p and x depend on v linearly, suggesting the same transformation. This is key to creating $-Et+px$ because normally one would not necessarily link (p, E) and (x, t) in the same equation.

The next idea is that of Lorentz invariant information which argue is key. m_0 , the rest mass (or $m_0 c^2$ the rest energy) may be viewed from many different frames, but one still has the same

physical situation, i.e. there must be a frame invariant piece of information linked to m_0 . If one is using matrices, then it is natural to consider a modulus as the invariant, but if $E > m_0 c^2$, then one must use an unusual metric:

$$\begin{vmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{vmatrix} \quad ((3))$$

This then leads to: $-E^2 + p^2 = m_0^2 c^4$ ($c=1$) ((4)).

There are then three reasons for the Lorentz invariant: $-Et + px$:

- (A) (p, E) and (x, t) transform under the same Lorentz matrix
- (B) There exists an invariant modulus linked with this matrix which fixes the form of the matrix.
- (C) The modulus involves a metric ((3)) with a minus sign.

Given all of these reasons, one may consider $A = -Et + px$ as representing a Lorentz invariant piece of information for a set of (p, E) and (x, t) for different frames which all linked to m_0 at $x=0, t=0, v=0$. ((4)), however, immediately leads to degenerate A values if:

$$x = x_0 + n \cdot \hbar / p \quad t = t_0 + n \cdot \hbar / E \quad \text{where } n = \text{integer} \quad ((5))$$

It is possible, however, to describe a free particle without considering $-Et + px$ at all, namely through:

$$E = m_0 c^2 / \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2} \quad p = m_0 v / \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2} \quad \text{one dimension and } x - x_0 = v(t - t_0) \quad ((6))$$

There is nothing wrong with ((5)) and it displays no degeneracies. As a result, a person using ((6)) would not consider the degeneracies at all, i.e. would use classical mechanics instead of quantum mechanics.

This leads to the main point of this note. Why does one need to consider $-Et + px$? The degeneracies only appear if $-Et + px$, not even other invariants such as $-E^2 + p^2 = m_0^2 c^4$ ($c=1$) or $ct^2 - x^2 = \text{invariant}$ display it.

We suggest that if one wishes to have a Lorentz invariant view which equates all moving frame views of a particle at $x=0, t$ with $m_0, v=0$, then one needs to use a Lorentz invariant to describe this piece of information. It is this piece of information equated to the same values in all frames for a certain $(p, E), (x, t)$ in the frame in question which shows equivalence. Simply using $x=vt$ in each frame does not show any equivalence between the frames, even though they describe the same physical state m_0 at $x=0, t, v=0$.

Thus, we argue that one cannot escape considering the Lorentz invariant information $-Et + px$. This, however, has consequences.

Consequences of Degenerate x,t Solutions of $A = -Et + px$

Given an x_0, t_0 and its corresponding A , A represents information about a particle with E, p at x_0, t_0 . One may, however, use ((5)) to obtain an infinite set of x, t points yielding the same A value, which is the Lorentz invariant information. This suggests that one has the same A for x_0, t_0 and $x_0 + 1 \cdot \hbar/p$ and $t_0 + \hbar/E$. In other words, one has a resolution issue. One cannot say that x_0 is better than $x_0 + \hbar/p$ etc. The information A applies to all of the degenerate x, t points. This does not imply that the particle does not follow $x = vt$ and (x, t) points of the trajectory have nothing to do with the degenerate grid points, except for the fact that one cannot really resolve all x and t points with finite resolution.

The degenerate resolution pieces $n \cdot \hbar/p$ and $n \cdot \hbar/E$ lead to $A = 0$, i.e. to add any Lorentz invariant information. This holds if one transforms them using a Lorentz transformation as expected:

$$p' = \gamma(p + vE) \quad E' = \gamma(E + vp) \quad p'/E' = v' = \frac{p + vE}{E + vp} \quad t' = \gamma(t + vx)$$

$$-E't' + p'x' = -(\gamma(p + vE))(\gamma(E + vp)) + (\gamma(p + vE))(\gamma(E + vp)) = 0 \quad \text{with } \gamma = 1/\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2} \quad ((7))$$

Trying to use these gradations in $-Et + px = \text{invariant}$, however, does not seem to lead to any interesting results because the gradations are not about a trajectory in space-time. They are only E, p dependent gradations which remove all information from A , i.e. make $A = 0$. Thus, it is somewhat unusual taking $A = -Et + px$, for which x and t represent motion in time and space, and trying to define t and x values which make $A = 0$, i.e. depend on E and p , the dynamical variables instead of being independent of them.

In other words, a resolution grid of x and t gradations seems to exist because of the Lorentz invariant $-Et + px$, but only because one tries to absorb E, p information into spatial and temporal gradations to make $A = 0$. In $-Et + px$, one may use any x, t values on wishes because for a fixed E, p , there are many trajectories $(x - x_0) = v(t - t_0)$ because one can choose any (x_0, t_0) .

Consider m_0 at $x = 0, t, v = 0$. Then: $A = -m_0 t$ ($c = 1$). Thus, in the rest frame different t values define the A values of the trajectory. One could, however, have m_0 at $x = x_0$ at $t, v = 0$ and $A = -m_0 t$ again. Thus, different t values in the rest frame describe Lorentz invariant information A in another frame. The 2×2 Lorentz transformation, acting on (x, t) in the rest frame (x, t) yields:

$$x' = \gamma(x + vt) \quad t' = \gamma(t + vx) \quad \text{or} \quad x' - vt' = \gamma(1 - v^2)x \quad ((8a)) \quad , \quad \text{but} \quad x' - vt' = x' - vt'o \quad ((8b))$$

In ((8b)) one may use any x' and t' value one wishes so there is no restriction on $x' - vt'o$, but in ((8a)) this linear combination must be $\gamma(1 - v^2)x$ where x is in the rest frame. This seems like an extra restriction. In other words, the Lorentz invariant information $-Et + px$ is linked with ((8a)). The origin in the rest frame is completely arbitrary and one can always make $x = 0$, but this suggests that $x' - vt' = 0$ while ((8b)) does not suggest this. Thus, the Lorentz transformation leads to a particular trajectory in the x', t' frame, i.e. imposes an extra restriction which is not really present. In order, however, to have the notion of a Lorentz invariant information, one must use

x', t' values which follow from using a Lorentz transformation of an (x, t) in the rest frame. It is the Lorentz matrix which is used to prove that $-Et+px$ is an invariant.

Quantum Considerations

We have argued above that the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et+px$ must be considered as it represents Lorentz invariant information and it leads to degenerate x, t points which yield $A=0$. We called these resolution points for t and x because all information is removed from A (i.e. $A=0$) so that x_0 and $x_0+h\bar{v}/p$ have the same A value and so there is a spatial resolution issue. One cannot have infinite x resolution. At the same time, p and E exist presumably at all x points and from $x=vt$, there is the sense of x and t being smooth (having uniform probability). This suggests that one use $\exp(-iEt)\exp(ipx)$ to describe the situation probabilistically. This function must be periodic and respect the given resolutions, but must also be linked with uniform x and t .

Conclusion

In conclusion, we try to argue that the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et+px$ for a free particle is not only relevant, but cannot be ignored because it provides the same A information for (p, E) (x', t') in any frame moving at constant $-v$ and viewing $m_0, v=0$ at $x=0, t$ in a rest frame. Physically, all of these views represent the same object and there must be a Lorentz invariant piece of information to capture this. The issue is that A has degenerate x values, so this information is linked with $x_0+n\hbar/hp$ and $t_0+n\hbar/E$, where n is an integer. This implies non-infinite resolution if A is to be taken seriously. A , incidentally, is the relativistic and nonrelativistic classical action if $x/t=v$ and so is taken seriously. These degenerate values only appear if one considers the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$ and not by examining $x'=vt'$. This implies that the Lorentz invariant information is more fundamental and even imposes resolution restrictions on $x'=vt'$. The point seems to be that different $x'=vt'$ do not explicitly show a connection to the same $m_0, v=0$ at $x=0, t$ state whereas $-Et+px$ does. (p, E) and (x, t) transform under the same Lorentz matrix and this together with an invariant modulus and the minus sign in the metric allow one to remove all information from A by making x and t, p and E dependent. This leads to $A=0$ or resolution points which may yield the same A value suggesting noninfinite resolution. Normally in classical physics, clock and ruler gradations are not linked to the energy or momentum of an object, but are considered fixed, but introducing energy and p related gradations is a way to remove information from A making it 0, thus making it impossible to distinguish between x_0, t_0 and $x_0+h\bar{v}/p$ and $t_0+h\bar{v}/E$ using a Lorentz invariant piece of information.